

DAMAGE/WEIGHT LOSS RELATIONSHIP OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER THERMAL AGEING

X. Colin, C. Marais and J.P. Favre

*Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aéropatiales,
Département Matériaux et Systèmes Composites,
29, avenue de la division Leclerc, BP 72, Châtillon, 92322 Cedex, France*

SUMMARY: With the intention of being used as structural materials for the next generation supersonic aircraft, carbon/polymer composites were put into context by subjecting them to accelerated thermal ageing conditions. Damage observed on two unidirectional composites (T800/F655-2 and IM7/977-2) and their corresponding neat resin aged for several thousands hours in air at various temperatures is described and discussed. The analysis is conducted following two approaches : a local approach that displays both oxidation of the matrix and cracking of composite free edges and a global approach that shows the material weight evolution. Subsequently, different degradation modes take place at the same time for each of three principal directions of the unidirectional composite. The magnitude of damages significantly depends on fibre orientation of free surfaces exposed to environment.

KEYWORDS: polymer matrix, durability, ageing, damage, oxidation, weight loss.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon/polymer composites are likely to be used as structural materials for the next generation supersonic aircraft and thus will have to face severe service conditions. Particularly, they will have to undergo a minimum of 25,000 thermal cycles within the temperature range -55°C/+120°C including 60,000 supersonic flight hours at 120°C in oxidizing atmosphere. From previous studies [1, 2], a gradual modification of the composite structure under accelerated thermal ageing conditions was found. Damage is a combination between oxidation and thermally induced cracking. Thus, accurate testing and adequate modelling are required to give to the prediction of long-term behaviour a good reliability.

The present paper focuses on the damage resulting from the combined action of oxygen and isothermal temperature. Since attention is drawn here to the damage of free edges, this paper is limited to unidirectional composites.

To observe overall degradation process, three different specimen types, composite and neat resin, were specially machined so as to amplify the corresponding degradation mode.

To accelerate degradation mechanisms, all these materials were aged for several thousands hours in air at higher temperatures than the supersonic flight temperature. Then, the analysis is presented following two approaches. A local approach, treated by conventional methods such

as optical microscopy and X-radiography, describes the development of the damaged zone in each of the principal directions of composite materials at different ageing times. At the same time, a global approach shows the material weight evolution for every isothermal ageing.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

Materials

Composite systems were selected for this study by an previous assessment of the oxidative stability of fibre/resin systems currently used in aircraft composite structures. The two selected materials are made of carbon fibre/bismaleimide resin (Hexel T800H/F655-2) and carbon fibre/epoxy resin (Cyttec Fiberite IM7/977-2).

Unidirectional composite and neat resin plates were processed with the same moulding conditions in accordance with their respective recommended resin cure cycles then a post-cure under primary vacuum. In the two unidirectional composites, the fibre volume fraction was estimated to be 65%. All the materials, composites and neat resins, were inspected prior to testing. Then, composite plates were cut into rectangular specimens, 50mm long, 30mm large and 1mm thick, which are approximate sizes so as to obtain the three different types showed in figure 1. Meanwhile, neat resin plates were cut into rectangular specimens of about 20mm long, 10mm wide and 1.5 mm thick.

Figure 1: Cutting of unidirectional composite samples for ageing tests. Principal axes (1, 2, 3) are defined by fibre orientation.

Test methods

The composites and respective neat resin samples were aged in air-circulating ovens for several thousands hours. Thermal tests were performed over the glass temperature range for each of

the materials respectively. These isothermal tests were at 150, 180, 210 and 240°C for the bismaleimide-based materials and 150, 180 and 200°C for the epoxy-based materials. Most of the samples were removed from ovens at definite ageing times and examined either by optical microscopy after polishing of cross-sections or by radiography after impregnating with zinc iodide. Other samples were removed intermittently, cooled at room temperature in a dessiccator, weighed and returned to the oven.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Local approach – Damage analysis

For every material, micrographs and radiographs show a continuous change of the structure of free edges as a function of ageing time. The rate of this development depends on both resin nature and severity of ageing conditions.

Neat resin

Figure 2 shows micrographs of cross-sections of neat resin specimens aged at 180°C in air. The chemical attack on the specimens is revealed by a different polishing relief between the material free surfaces and the material core. Damaged regions, which present a better polishing relief than protected regions, appear as lighted areas.

Pertaining to polymer chain oxidation [1, 2], the chemical reactions are limited to material free edges and spares material cores. Since the polishing relief of material free edges improves versus ageing temperature and time, the oxidation degree is assumed to increase as a function of the severity of ageing conditions.

Figure 2: View of oxidized layer (lighted region) on polished neat resin cross-section corners with ageing conditions of 4000 hours at 180°C in air.

The development of these apparent oxidized layers has been determined from these micrographs. Estimated oxidized layer thickness is plotted versus ageing time in Figure 3. The oxygen chemical attack first affects the free surfaces in contact with environment and then induces a damage which progresses as a decreasing function of ageing time inside the material. The propagation rate of this oxidation front moving towards the material core seems to be independent of ageing temperature. Subsequently, the oxidized layer thickness tends towards an asymptotic value which is also independent of ageing temperature.

Besides, oxidation fronts within F655-2 specimens, grow faster and deeper towards sample cores than those within 977-2 specimens. Asymptotic value is located around 280 μm for F655-2 neat resin against 120 μm for 977-2. Consequently, in a first approximation, it appears that 977-2 neat resin is less sensitive to the thermo-oxidation than F655-2 or oxygen diffusion through 977-2 neat resin is slower than that F655-2.

Figure 3: Growth of apparent oxidized layer thickness versus ageing time determined on micrographs of neat resin samples aged in air at various temperatures.

Unidirectional composite

Figure 4 shows micrographs and radiographs of unidirectional composite specimens aged at 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in air. Cracking of free edges and superimposed matrix oxidation accelerate damage propagation towards the material core. New matrix surfaces created on both sides of the cracks are attacked by oxygen widening cracks progressively. Though the oxidized layer thickness of all matrix surfaces subjected to environment is assumed to be limited to average values determined on neat resin specimens, cracking induces an irregular oxidation front next to composite free edges. Consequently, the damaged zone presents a variable thickness.

Micrographs reveal that the crack volume content of free edges depends on fibre orientation of free surfaces exposed to environment. Thus, few cracks are observed in the transverse direction 3. The thin resin layer which covers the as-processed surface S_3 seems to prevent crack initiation.

Actually, most of the cracks are essentially initiated around fibre tips of surfaces S_1 and S_2 during cutting. Then, crack growth towards the material core only depends on fibre

orientation. Since they meet no obstacles in the fibre direction 1, cracks preferably develop along the fibre/matrix interface which leads to the widest cracked volume part. On the contrary, crack propagation in the transverse direction 2 is strongly reduced and even stopped by perpendicular fibres. Consequently, cracked volume part remains confined near the free surface S_2 .

Radiograph examinations confirm the damage development depends on fibre orientation. Cracked free edges filled with zinc iodide and projected in the radiograph plane appear as dark areas in Figure 4. Since the dark area is the sum of all cracks of each free edge, obtained profiles are continuous and regular. As expected, the largest amount of absorbed zinc iodide is observed in the fibre direction 1 whereas only traces of zinc iodide are detected in the transverse directions 2 and 3. Consequently, corrosion is assumed to be only limited to matrix oxidation in the transverse directions 2 and 3. On the contrary, corrosion is assumed to be a combination of both oxidation and cracking in the fibre direction 1.

Figure 4: View of the cracking of free edges on IM7/977-2 unidirectional composite specimens with ageing conditions of 4000 hours at 180°C in air.

The extent of the apparent cracked zone has been assessed in the fibre direction from these radiographs. Estimated crack zone thickness at 180°C is plotted against ageing time in Figure 5. For comparison, oxidized layer thickness of corresponding neat resin specimens aged in the same conditions is mentioned.

After an induction time corresponding to crack initiation on the free surface S_1 , each crack length separately increases as a function of ageing time. Consequently, no maximum crack length is expected to be reached. Since the crack propagation is faster than the movement of oxidation front in neat resin specimens, each crack tip might only be very slightly oxidized. On the other hand, crack propagation increases with ageing temperature.

Figure 5 : Growth of apparent cracked zone versus ageing time in the fibre direction 1 assessed on radiographs of unidirectional composite samples. Comparison with the apparent oxidized layer thickness of neat resin specimens. All the materials aged at 180°C in air.

Micrographs and radiographs show few difference about sensibility to cracking of two composite systems. Cracked zone of IM7/977-2 appears to be slightly wider than that for T800/F655-2 in the fibre direction 1 as indicated in Figure 5. However, these additional matrix surfaces can strongly accelerate matrix oxidation and induce consequences on weight evolution particularly.

Global approach – Weight evolution measurements

Figures 6 and 7 show weight variation curves of the three kinds of composite samples during isothermal ageing in air. To compare the weight evolution between the matrix and the corresponding neat resin, this one has been reduced to a mass amount of matrix contained in composite specimens.

Weight variation curves imply a continuous modification of the chemical structure of free edges. The rate of this chemical evolution depends on both resin nature and severity of ageing conditions, carbon fibre being assumed inert at these ageing temperatures. Besides, curves of two resins depict two different thermo-oxidative behaviours.

In Figures 6 and 7, curves of two neat resins present a first weight loss attributed to the moisture removing. Then, a weight increasing followed by a linear weight decreasing are observed for F655-2 neat resin. Thus, oxygen bonding is preponderant on polymer chain scission and also product volatilization in the first ageing times. But, after a balance of the magnitude of these two phenomena, afterwards degradation mechanisms prevail over oxygen bonding.

On the contrary, for the 977-2 neat resin, curve is limited to a monotonous weight decreasing. Degradation mechanisms are preponderant for the first ageing times and thus, might mask a possible oxygen bonding. At the beginning of ageing time, degradation rate is very fast, then it is more and more slow.

Although oxidized layer of 977-2 neat resin is thicker than that of the F655-2 resin, the first one losses more weight. It is deduced that degradation acts are more numerous in 977-2 than F655-2. Thus it appears clearly that the oxidized layer thickness of neat resin specimens is not the parameter to take in consideration to explain their weight variation. We have rather to consider neat resin nature and chemical reaction mechanisms as responsible parameters for oxygen bonding and removing of various volatils which, both, lead to the weight development [4, 5].

For all composite sample shapes, curves present the same degradation stages that for their corresponding neat resin. Eventually, matrix oxidation appears as the main degradation mode in unidirectional composite degradation.

Besides, when matrix surface areas exposed to environment present no cracks then composite weight variation is next to neat resin weight variation (see UD2 and UD3 composites in Figure 6). On the contrary, when cracks appear, additional matrix surface areas due to these new crack lengths are exposed to oxygen chemical attack. Consequently, degradation stages are amplified as seen about weight variation curves and highlight perfectly interaction between oxidation and cracking. It is the case for all two UD1 composites in Figures 6 and 7. Since matrix oxidized layer thickness is approximately the same as well on free surfaces as around the cracks, the weight difference Δm between neat resin weight variation and composite weight variation give a possibility to determine matrix surface areas attacked by oxygen around the cracks.

Figure 6: Weight evolution versus ageing time of T800/F655-2 composite samples and their corresponding neat resin reduced to mass amount contained in composite specimens.

All materials aged at 180°C in air.

Figure 7: Weight evolution versus ageing time of IM7/977-2 composite samples and their corresponding neat resin reduced to mass amount contained in composite specimens. All materials aged at 180°C in air.

The magnitude of all these different degradation stages depends on ageing temperature. Over a temperature range limited between 150°C and 240°C, the amount of oxygen bonding increases when ageing temperature decreases. On the contrary, the rate of degradation mechanisms increases when ageing temperature arises.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that examinations of weight evolution and micrographs and radiographs are quite complementary for a damage analysis on unidirectional composites and corresponding neat resins. Whatever the material, weight variation quantifies chemical modifications coming from free edges attacked by oxygen. However, the oxidized layer thickness, well identified on neat resin, is not proportional to the weight variation. Matrix oxidation has been found to be the principal degradation mode in transverse directions 2 and 3 of unidirectional composites. In the fibre direction 1, there is an interaction between matrix oxidation and cracking of free edges. The overall phenomena must be considered to give a good prediction of long-term behaviour.

Adequate modelling using kinetic model relevant to oxidation of polymer [3, 4] and taking into account additional matrix surfaces created around cracks is in progress. Results will be published in a next paper.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors would like to acknowledge J.P. Favre (retired) for many helpful discussions and Aerospatiale Suresnes (CCR) for supplying carbon/resin composites.

REFERENCES

[1] Favre J.-P., Levadoux H., Ochin T. & Cinquin J., "Ageing of organic matrix composites at moderate temperatures - A first assessment", *10th National Conf. on Comp. Mat. (JNC-10)*, edited by D. Baptiste & A. Vautrin, Vol. 1, 1996, pp 205-214, (AMAC, Paris, 1996).

[2] Nam J.D. & Seferis J.C., "Anisotropic thermo-oxidative stability of carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composites", *SAMPE Quarterly*, Vol. 24, N° 1, 1992, pp 10.

[3] Audoin L., Langlois V., Verdu J. & de Bruijn J.C.M., "Role of oxygen diffusion in polymer ageing: kinetic and mechanical aspects", *J. of Mat. Science*, Vol. 29, 1994, pp 569.

[4] Bolland J.L. & Gee G., "Kinetics studies in the chemistry of rubber and related materials. II. Thermochemistry and mechanisms of olefin oxidation", *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, Vol.42, 1946, pp 244.